

Effects of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation on Achievement and Retention in Physics among College of Education Students in Niger State

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Abstract

The study investigated effects of computer-laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics, specifically in the latent heat of fusion of ice, among colleges of education students in Niger state. The design for the study was quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, post-test non-randomized, non-equivalent control group design. Four research questions and corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study consists of all Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) level one Physics students in Colleges of Education during the 2022/2023 academic session in Niger state. The sample of the study consists of 57 (30 male and 27 Female) level one physics students in Niger state, two intact classes were used. The instrument used in this study was Physics Practical Achievement Test (PPAT) as a test instrument. The PPAT comprised of 25-item multiple-choice type questions, validated by experts and its reliability coefficient was calculated to be 0.82, using Kuder-Richardson (KR₂₀). Data gathered were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Independent t-test statistics. The study revealed that experimental group achieved more than the control, and the difference in the achievements was statistically significant $t(67) = 3.21, p=0.002, (P<0.05)$. The difference in the achievement of male and female students in the experimental group was not statistically significant, $t(25) = .19, p=0.85, (P>0.05)$. It was therefore concluded that the students' achievement and retention are better attained when simulation method is used in teaching. It was recommended that science teachers should be trained to produce indigenous Simulation Software.

Keywords: Physics, Latent Heat, Computer Simulation, Achievement, Retention

Introduction

One motive of integrating technology especially computer software technology such as computer simulation models in education is to improve teaching strategies and consequently improve students' academic achievement and retention. Computer Simulation Strategy in this study refers to the method of teaching Physics practical through the use of computer. Simulation, according to Apau (2020) is a specially designed animated model that looks like a live environment in which learners can experience different real-life situations. Computer Simulation Strategy was also defined in Emmanuel, Maxwell and Shuaibu (2016) as the process of using a computer to imitate the operation of a real world process or facility according to appropriately developed assumptions taking the form of logical, statistical or mathematical relationships which are developed into a model. A simulation program can be based on hypothetical situations to study how a system works (Haruna, 2019). These kinds of programs allow the learners to modify the variables in the provided virtual scenario in order to study the effect of the variables on the processes. Basically, Computer Simulation Strategy allows the learners to master their skills or tasks without facing any risks, (Apau, 2020).

Computer simulation, especially in Physics practical brings about great academic achievements to the students through an open learning environment, which gives students opportunities to develop an understanding of physical phenomena and laws by developing hypotheses and testing ideas, to develop an understanding of the relations between physical concepts, variables and phenomena by isolating and manipulating parameters, to utilize a variety of representations, including pictures, animations, graphs, vectors and numerical data displays, which help them understand the underlying concepts, relationships and processes in physics. It also gives them opportunities to demonstrate their portrayal and mental models of the physical world and to

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employ an investigative approach about phenomena that are difficult to experience in a classroom or laboratory environments, due to their complexity, technical difficulty, money or time consumption, or because they occur too fast to be understood by just observing them in real-life settings, example in nuclear fission or fusion experiments, (Abdullahi, 2021).

Review of Related Empirical Studies

A lot of similar studies have been carried out by different scholars in different places at different times. Some studies significant to the current one are reviewed below.

On academic achievement, using the computer simulation strategy to teach Physics, the study of Gambari and Yusuf (2015) indicated that a significant difference, $F(1, 81) = 5.092$, $p = .027$ in students' achievement in favor of those in the experimental group (those exposed to Computer-Assisted Strategy, STAD). The result also indicated no significant difference, $F(1, 43) = 0.852$, $p = 0.361$, in the achievement of male and female students taught physics using computer-assisted STAD cooperative setting. Lastly the study indicates that there was significant difference, $F(1, 81) = 3.870$, $p = 0.053$ in the retention test of students taught physics using computer-assisted STAD and those exposed to traditional method.

The study of Igweh (2012) revealed that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 114) = 4.057$, $p = 0.046$ between the mean scores of students taught basic electronics with computer tutorial drill and those taught using conventional teaching methods in the achievement test. The result also indicated no significant difference, F -value (3.774), significance of F (.055) and confidence level of 0.05, in the achievement of male and female students taught physics using computer simulation. Similarly the study revealed that the students taught basic electronics with computer tutorial and drill retained their learning better than those taught with the conventional teaching methods. Analysis of covariance showed F -value (157.009), significance of F (.000) and confidence level of .05. Similar results in the study of Gambari and Yusuf (2015).

Another significant study to the current one is that of Olorukooba, Sani and Kazeem (2016). The study revealed that there was significant difference, $t(98) = 3.51$, $p=0.001$, ($P<0.05$) on the achievement of students taught Qualitative Analysis Concept of Chemistry using Computer Simulations performed better than those taught with traditional method alone. The result showed that there was no significant difference, $t(48) = 0.33$, $p=0.75$, ($P>0.05$) in the average performance of male and female students taught Qualitative Analysis Concepts of Chemistry using Computer Simulations. The study also revealed that there was significant difference, $t(98) = 4.51$, $p=0.001$, ($P<0.05$) in the academic retention between students taught Qualitative Analysis Concept of Chemistry using Computer Simulations and those exposed to traditional method alone. The findings in Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) agreed with those of Gambari and Yusuf (2015) and Igweh (2012).

In the study of Adam, Mamuda, Adedoh. and Isaiah (2021), it was revealed that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 331) = 20.230$, $p = .000$, in the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Educational Technology, EDT, using computer simulation and those exposed to conventional method. And also that gender has no significant effect on students' achievement in EDT when exposed to computer simulation, $F(1, 329) = .50$, $p = .48$.

Findings on academic retention based on gender according to Nkok (2021) showed no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught sexual reproduction in plant with computer simulation strategy, $F(1, 15.7)=0.921$, $p=.340$. But Egara and Mosimege's (2023) study did not support earlier Nkok's (2021) finding on gender retention. It was revealed in Egara and Mosimege (2023) that there was a significant gender difference, $F(1, 110)=6.947$ and $p=.010$, in the mean retention scores of students taught algebra using a computer simulation approach, with the female students faring better.

Statement of the Research Problem

Some research studies including those of Ewansih and Omorogbe (2013) and Benson (2017) on the use of laboratory to teach Physics practical in Nigerian schools have been carried out. Such studies have revealed some problems such as decline rather than improvement in the teaching of Physics practical to students; in addition, there is inadequacy of facilities in many of our schools' laboratories. While the studies of Danjuma and Adeleye (2015) and Abdullahi (2021) showed that a big problem to the effective teaching of Physics in some colleges is not lack of the necessary laboratory or equipment but rather lack of their usage, probably due to problem of lack of knowledge of using the equipment by the teachers. In the absence of laboratories

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and laboratory equipment, teaching and learning of Physics concepts face great problems and poor achievement and retention may result.

One such concept that suffers misconception according to Chavan (2013) and Madu and Orji (2015), is Heat and Thermodynamics. The concepts of heat and thermodynamics in Physics pose many problems to students as a result of misconception resulting to low achievement. Therefore, the problem of this research is to determine the effects of computer-laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics, specifically in the concept of latent heat of fusion of ice, among colleges of education students in Niger state.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to determine the effects of computer-laboratory-simulation on achievement and retention in Physics (latent heat of fusion of ice) among colleges of education students in Niger state. The specific objectives were to:

1. To determine the difference between the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught Specific Latent Heat of Fusion (SLHF) of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies.
2. To find the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught Specific Latent Heat of Fusion, SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy.
3. To determine the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
4. To determine the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?
2. Is there any difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy?
3. What are the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?
4. Is there any difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

- HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
- HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy.
- HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.
- HO₄: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Methodology

Design

Quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of all Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) one Physics students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Colleges of Education in Niger state. The sample used for the study consisted of 57 (38 males and 19 females) NCE I Physics students. The study was carried out in two Colleges of Education in Niger state, Federal College of Education (FCE) Kontagora and College of Education (COE) Minna. NCE I Physics students of FCE Kontagora were purposively assigned as the Experimental Group, EG. While the NCE I Physics students of COE Minna, being the Control group, CG.

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Table 1. Research design layout

Groups	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest	Retention
Experimental Group	O ₁	X ₁	O ₂	O ₃
Control Group	O ₁	X ₀	O ₂	O ₃

Where: O₁, O₁ = Observation of pre-test for the experimental and control groups
 O₂, O₂ = Observation of post-test for the experimental and control groups
 O₃, O₃ = Observation of retention for the experimental and control groups
 X₁ = Treatment for Experimental Group
 X₀ = No Treatment

Instrumentation

A Physics Practical Achievement Test (PPAT), was developed to test students' achievement and retention in the concepts of heat, calorimetry. Thus, The (PPAT) was based on NCE I syllabus on concepts of Heat. It consisted of 25 objective test questions which were developed for use at pre-test, post-test and retention (Achievement tests). Each correct answer attracted a score of one mark, total marks were converted to percentage to arrive at the total scores.

Computer simulation software used as the treatment instrument in the study was SIMLAB Physics Laboratory Simulation Model, developed and uploaded on the web as a freeware by Tarara (2011).

Validation of the Research Instrument

The PPAT was validated by two experts, a senior lecturer and a chief lecturer in the Department of Physics, FCE Kontagora. The experts' observations / recommendations were taken into consideration and corrections effected.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

To determine the reliability coefficient of the treatment instrument (PPAT), pilot tests were conducted at FCE, Zuba. FCE Zuba is not part of the population but it shares similar characteristics with the sampled Colleges of Education. A total of 30 students were used for the pilot study, the trial test. The results obtained from the trial tests conducted were used for reliability test of the instrument. Kuder-Richardson (KR₂₀) formula was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the (PPAT) to be 0.82

Experimental Procedure/Administration of the Instrument

Cooperation of the Physics heads of department of the two institutions, laboratory technicians and the students were sought. In order not to disrupt the academic activities of the schools, the research work was scheduled to lecture-free periods of the students. Before the treatment, pretests were administered to both experimental and control groups using the instrument described above.

Variables of teacher's qualities were controlled by the researchers themselves to introduce the Physics practical lessons to the participating students. The control group received instructions on the practical Conventional strategy on SLHF of ice experiment, while experimental group was given the treatment on the same SLHF of ice through computer simulation strategy, using the simulation model. The treatment lasted for two weeks. Immediately after the treatment, posttest was administered to the two groups. The administration of delayed test was after two weeks so as to test students' retention. Reports of experiments performed based on the given instruments were used to collect data.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. The independent sample t-test analysis was used to test all the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Computer software Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0 was used for the data analysis.

Results

Research question one; What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategies?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Physics Achievement Scores for Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation and those Exposed to Conventional Laboratory Strategies.

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Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Gain Diff.
		Mean, \bar{x}	SD	Mean, \bar{x}_g	SD_g		
Experimental	27	30.19	7.50	58.80	13.22	28.61	10.91
Control	30	31.50	7.01	49.20	11.60	17.70	
Total	57						

Results in Table 2 showed that the mean gain of achievement of the experimental group ($\bar{x}_g = 28.61$, $SD_g = 13.22$, $n = 27$) was higher than that of the control group ($\bar{x}_g = 17.70$, $SD_g = 11.60$, $n = 30$). This indicates that the intervention (i.e. the use of the simulation strategy) have higher effect in improving physics students' academic achievement in SLHF of ice experiments than the use of the conventional teaching strategy. The mean gain difference was 10.91.

Research question two: Is there any difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy?

To answer this research question, mean and standard deviation were used and the result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Results of Male and Female Taught SLHF of ice with Computer Laboratory Simulation.

Instructional Mode	Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Gain Diff.
			Mean \bar{x}	SD	Mean \bar{x}_g	SD_g		
Simulation	Males	17	41.10	7.69	65.88	11.31	24.78	
	Females	10	39.22	6.28	66.72	10.01	27.50	2.72
	Total	27						

Table 3 showed that male students taught SLHF using the Simulation approach had ($\bar{x} = 41.10$, $SD = 7.69$) in the pretest and ($\bar{x}_g = 65.88$, $SD_g = 11.31$) in the posttest, giving a pretest-posttest achievement mean gain of ($\bar{x}_g = 24.78$). While, the female students treated equally achieved ($\bar{x} = 39.22$, $SD = 6.28$) in the pretest and ($\bar{x}_g = 66.72$, $SD_g = 10.01$) in the posttest, giving a pretest-posttest achievement mean gain of ($\bar{x}_g = 27.50$). The findings indicated a difference between the mean gain of the males and females (2.72) in favour of the female students. Inferential statistics was used to find the significance of this difference.

Research Question 3: What are the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation and those exposed to Conventional Strategy?

Table 4. Mean Retention and Standard Deviation of Retention Scores of Experimental Group and the Control Group

Group	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	Mean Diff.
Experimental	27	45.60	13.08	13.57
Control	30	32.03	24.42	
Total	57			

Table 4 shows the mean retention and standard deviation of achievement scores of experimental and control groups at posttest. From Table 4, it can be deduced that the mean and standard deviation scores at posttest for Experimental Group were ($\bar{x} = 45.60$, $SD = 13.08$), while those of the control group were ($\bar{x} = 32.03$, $SD = 24.42$). These give a mean difference of 13.57.

Research Question 4: What is the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female NCE I physics students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation?

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation of Retention Test Scores of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice Using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Gender	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	Mean Diff.
Males	17	52.67	13.78	3.49
Females	10	49.18	9.33	
Total	27			

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Table 5 reveals the mean retention and standard deviation of achievement scores of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy. From the Table, it is observed that there is a difference between the mean retention scores of the two groups at post-test where male students had mean achievement and standard deviation of ($\bar{x} = 52.67, SD = 13.78$), while their female counterparts had mean achievement and standard deviation of ($\bar{x} = 49.18, SD = 9.33$). Independent t-test was used to determine whether the mean difference of 3.49 is statistically significant.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.

Table 6. Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Achievement of Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Simulation and those Exposed to Conventional Strategies.

Method	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Simulation strategy	27	58.80	13.22	55	2.92	.005	Rejected
Conventional strategy	30	49.20	11.60				
Total	57						

Table 6 showed $t(55) = 2.92, p=0.005, (P<0.05)$. The null hypothesis was thus rejected because there was a significant difference in achievement between students' taught physics practical with Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy. Hence, it was established that students that were taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy had a higher score and significantly performed better than their counterparts that were exposed to Conventional Strategy.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE I students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy

Table 7: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Achievement of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice with Computer Simulation Strategy

Gender	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	17	65.88	11.31	25	.19	.85	Accepted
Female	10	66.72	10.01				
Total	27						

Table 7 showed no significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught SLHF of ice with Computer Simulation Strategy. The table showed $t(25) = .19, p=0.85, (P>0.05)$. The null-hypothesis was thus accepted because there was no significant difference between the achievement of male and female students taught physics practical with Computer Simulation Strategy. Hence, it was established that the achievement of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation approach did not differ.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I physics students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to Conventional Strategy.

Table 8: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Retention Test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Experimental	27	45.60	13.08	55	2.57	0.01	Rejected
Control	28	42.11	13.08				

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Control	30	32.03	24.42
Total	57		

Table 8 revealed the independent t-test comparison of retention test scores of the Experimental and Control groups. An examination of the table shows that there was significant difference in the retention scores of the two groups, $t(55) = 2.57$, $p = .01$, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, H_0_3 was rejected. This implies that there was actually a significant difference in the retention of students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy and those exposed to SLHF of ice with Conventional Strategy.

HO₄: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students when taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy

Table 9: Summary of Independent Sample T-test on the Retention Test Scores of Male and Female Students Taught SLHF of Ice Using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Gender	N	Mean Ret. (\bar{x})	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Males	17	52.67	13.78	25	0.71	.49	Accepted
Females	10	49.18	9.33				
Total	27						

Table 9 shows the independent t-test result of the comparison of retention scores of experimental group based on gender. An examination of the table shows $t(25) = 0.71$, $p = .49$, ($P > 0.05$). On the basis of this, hypothesis four was retained. Therefore, there was no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in research question one which deals with the students' academic achievement mean scores in SLHF of ice when taught with the Simulation Strategy and when exposed to Conventional laboratory method, revealed that there was a mean gain difference of 10.91 in favor of the experimental group. Also, the t-test analysis in hypothesis one revealed that the difference in the mean achievement scores was statistically significant, showed $t(55) = 2.92$, $p = 0.005$, ($P < 0.05$). This is an indication that the use of the Simulation Strategy has higher effect on students' academic achievement in teaching SLHF of ice. The study affirms the study of Adam, *et al.* (2021) that there was a significant difference, $F(1, 331) = 20.230$, $p = .000$, in the mean academic achievement scores of students taught Educational Technology, EDT, using computer simulation and those exposed to conventional method. The finding in this study is also in tandem with earlier studies of Igweh (2012), Gambari and Yusuf (2015) and Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016), that students taught using computer simulation achieved significantly more than those exposed to traditional strategy.

Findings in research question two showed that the mean achievement scores of female participants was 66.72 which was higher but not statistically significant than that of their male counterparts which had a mean achievement of 65.88. The result showed that $t(25) = .19$, $p = 0.85$, ($P > 0.05$). This means that the observed higher achievement of female students over their male counterparts was not statistically significant. This result again supports the earlier findings of Gambari and Yusuf (2015), Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) and Adam, *et al.* (2021). These indicated that there was no significant differences in the achievement of male and female students taught using computer simulation.

Findings in research question three on the mean retention scores of students taught SLHF of ice using the Computer Simulation and Conventional Laboratory Strategies indicates a mean difference of 13.57. The t-test analysis showed that the difference is statistically significant. An examination of table 8 shows that there was a significant difference in the mean retention scores of the two groups, $t(55) = 2.57$, $p = .01$, ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis three was rejected. This study also agrees with the earlier studies of Igweh (2012) and Olorukooba, *et al.* (2016) that teaching sciences using Simulation Strategy significantly enhances students' retention.

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Findings on the influence of gender on the retention scores of students exposed to Computer Simulation Strategy revealed a mean retention difference of 3.49 in favor of the males. However, this difference was not statistically significant, $t(25) = 0.71$, $p = .49$, ($P > 0.05$). As such there was no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught SLHF of ice using Computer Simulation Strategy. The finding agrees with the earlier finding of Nkok (2021) but disagreed with that of Egara and Mosimege (2023) which revealed that there was a significant gender difference, $F(1, 110) = 6.947$ and $p = .010$, in the mean retention scores of students taught using computer simulation.

Conclusion

The study investigated effects of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation on achievement and retention in the concept of latent heat among colleges of education students in Niger state. It was revealed that the students that were taught SLHF of ice with the computer simulation strategy have achieved more than those exposed to the same topic with Conventional Laboratory Strategy. The difference in the achievement was statistically significant. The difference in the mean achievement scores of male students over that of their female counterparts was not statistically significant. Results of the study also revealed that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean retention scores of NCE I Physics students taught SLHF of ice with the Computer Simulation and those expose to Conventional Strategies.

Recommendations

Based on findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Computer Simulation Strategy should be used to supplement Conventional Laboratory method of teaching to improve students' achievement and retention in physics.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to teach Physics using Computer Simulation Strategy in the absence of laboratory equipment.
3. The use of Computer Laboratory Simulation Strategy should be encouraged where it is found that students have low retention in the course of learning. Computer Simulation Strategy builds academic retention in students as revealed here.

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